

Review

Bioprinting and synthetic biology approaches to engineer functional endocrine pancreatic constructs

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Diabetes is a complex disease affecting over 500 million people worldwide. Traditional approaches, such as insulin delivery, are mainstay treatments, but do not cure the disease. Recent advances in biofabrication and synthetic biology offer new hope for the development of tissue constructs recapitulating salient organ functions. Here, we discuss recent progress in bioprinting a functional endocrine pancreas, ranging from cell sources to main advances in biomaterials. We review innovative areas for the development of this field, with a particular focus on the convergence of synthetic biology and cell engineering with bioprinting, which opens new avenues for developing advanced *in vitro* models and regenerative, transplantable grafts, with the potential to provide independence from exogenous insulin administration.

Bioprinting the endocrine pancreas to counter diabetes mellitus, an old but unsolved disease

The pancreas is a glandular organ with a key role during digestion and in the regulation of systemic metabolism. During development, it originates from the endoderm-derived posterior foregut, with progenitor cells giving rise to exocrine and endocrine cells (Box 1). The exocrine pancreas comprises acinar and ductal cells; its main role is to produce enzymes that are secreted into the duodenum to aid digestion. The endocrine pancreas accounts for 1–2% of pancreatic cells and comprises clusters of multiple hormone-secreting cells known as **islets of Langerhans** (see Glossary). The most abundant cell types in the islets are insulin-producing β cells (50–70% in humans) and glucagon-producing α cells (20% in humans), which enable fine tuning of circulating glucose levels. The progressive loss, dysfunction of insulin-producing β cells, or insulin resistance in peripheral tissues results in diabetes mellitus, the most common pancreatic disorder, which affects over 500 million people worldwide [1,2].

The most common types of diabetes are **type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM)** and **type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM)**, accounting for 5% and 90–95% of total cases respectively. Current treatments for T1DM and advanced T2DM involves the delivery of exogenous insulin to regulate glucose homeostasis. This is often combined with other drugs, such as insulin sensitizers and insulin release stimulators in the case of T2DM. Nevertheless, exogenous insulin administration requires constant glucose monitoring and does not recapitulate cell-mediated glucose control, impacting patients' quality of life, escalating healthcare costs, and leading to severe complications, including blindness, cardiovascular disease, nerve damage, and potentially fatal hypoglycemic events [3]. Transplantation of allogeneic islets has been investigated as a treatment for T1DM, but the accessibility of this therapy is limited by donor shortage and hampered by the need for immunosuppression and a risk of rejection. Thus, there is an urgent need to develop novel therapeutic approaches. Advanced

Highlights

Challenges to current treatments of diabetes highlight the urgent need to develop improved modeling platforms and therapies.

Bioprinting holds the potential to enable the generation of complex multicellular systems, crucial in pancreas tissue modeling, for instance to pattern islet and vascular channels.

Advances in protocols for differentiating pluripotent stem cells into islets pave the way for an unlimited source of cells for treatment, but more work is needed to improve their functionality and maturation.

Selection of biomaterials is crucial for creating functional pancreatic constructs that tackle current treatment limitations, namely cell survival, immunoevasion, and efficient grafting/vascularization.

Converging bioprinting and synthetic biology presents an exciting landscape for developing advanced models and therapies for diabetes.

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Box 1. Human pancreas developmental pathway for PSC differentiation

Human pluripotent stem cells (PSCs) have the potential to differentiate into the three main developmental cell lineages: ectoderm, endoderm, and mesoderm. During stem cell differentiation, it is crucial to guide these cells toward the final target phenotype, avoiding the induction toward a nontargeted lineage or undesired cell populations. An intuitive way for the development of protocols for differentiating PSCs into pancreatic endocrine cells is to recapitulate embryonic development *in vitro*. Developmental biology has shed light on the intricate processes of embryological patterning that lead to the generation of pancreatic endocrine cells and more specifically insulin-producing β cells [101,102], providing the necessary guidance to generate therapy-grade islets in the lab as well as highlighting the role of their surrounding environment.

The human pancreas emerges from the definitive endoderm germ layer (CXCR4+, FOXA2+, and SOX17+) [101,102], which is formed during the gastrulation step of embryonic development. The definitive endoderm gives rise to the primitive gut tube (FOXA2+, SOX17+, and HNF1B+), which, following further patterning, divide into three regions: foregut, midgut, and hindgut [101,102]. Pancreatic cell specification occurs in the posterior foregut (PDX1+, SOX9+) with the appearance of two buds comprising multipotent pancreatic progenitor cells (PDX1+, SOX9+, and NKX6.1+) [101,102]. Further expansion of these buds leads to fusion to generate a single organ, which is then divided into the central trunk and tip domains. Endocrine and duct progenitors differentiate from trunk cells; however, this bifurcation is not yet fully understood [103], with studies reporting endocrine specification and formation as budding islets [104] or endocrine specification as budding islets colocalized with endothelial cells, which limit ductal and acinar differentiation [13,105]. Pancreatic progenitor cells in the trunk domain give rise to endocrine progenitor cells (NEUROD1+, PDX1+, and NKX6.1+), which, upon further maturation, give rise to the mature endocrine cell populations in the islets of Langerhans, namely β (INS+, MAFA+, PDX1+), α (GCG+, ARX+, NGN3+), δ (SST+), and ϵ cells (GHR+) [101,102,106].

Importantly, each of the developmental stages during pancreatic commitment is characterized by the induction or suppression of specific genetic pathways, namely the partial activation of WNT and activation of TGF- β signaling during definitive endoderm specification. The activation and inhibition of different genetic pathways can be partially mimicked *in vitro* with protein or chemical activators/inhibitors and current differentiation protocols have been inspired by developmental biology to direct cell fate by replicating those environments *in vitro*.

technologies aiming to recreate engineered endocrine pancreatic tissues starting from unlimited cell sources, can open new opportunities for establishing regenerative tissue grafts to restore normoglycemia and advanced *in vitro* models to screen new drugs and further understand human pancreatic endocrine cells.

A major limitation to the development of new therapies for T1DM and T2DM is the poor predictive capacity of current *in vitro* and *in vivo* models. Studies on animal models have identified significant differences from humans in islet development, cytoarchitecture, and morphology. Conversely, current *in vitro* models are oversimplistic and lack the presence of surrounding cells, namely the stromal compartment, with increasing evidence showing that this compartment provides signals, such as morphogens and regulatory cytokines, which are vital for steering β cell maturation and functionality [4]. Moreover, another major limitation to the development of a curative treatment for T1DM is the high risk of long-term unsuccessful islet transplantation. Nearly 40% of transplants incur graft exhaustion or inadequate glucose control 1 year post implantation, a consequence of low islet engraftment and of toxicity associated with the immunosuppressive regimen [5,6].

Addressing these challenges, **tissue engineering (TE)**, more specifically **bioprinting**, allows the precise 3D placement of cells and biomaterials, enabling the generation of complex, multicellular systems with a defined architecture and matrix composition [7]. Converging bioprinting technologies, biomaterial development, advances in (stem) cell engineering, and especially **synthetic biology**, which can enable control over cellular behaviors and functions using engineered genetic circuits, provide an advanced technological toolkit for the design of bioinspired systems that recapitulate the architecture, composition, and salient functions of full organs.

Such innovations will enable researchers to more accurately reproduce the *in vivo* situation of the pancreas, including realistic parenchyma–stroma interactions, which are crucial for the development of novel and reliable *in vitro* models. Similarly, these advanced multicomponent tissues could allow

Glossary

Bioink: biomaterial used in bioprinting processes to encapsulate living cells and other molecules, creating a printable bioactive matrix. This serves as a scaffold for tissue formation during the bioprinting process.

Bioprinting: tissue engineering technology that involves the precise shaping of biological materials, such as cells, growth factors, and biomaterials, to create 3D structures that mimic natural tissues or organs.

Induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs): stem cells generated from somatic adult cells by means of cell reprogramming. Somatic cells are reverted to a pluripotent state similar to embryonic PSCs via induction of transcription factor expression, acquiring the potential to differentiate into the three main cell lineages (ectoderm, mesoderm, and endoderm).

Islets of Langerhans: clusters of endocrine cells dispersed throughout the exocrine pancreas responsible for the production and release of hormones involved in regulating blood sugar levels, such as insulin (β cells) and glucagon (α cells).

Pluripotent stem cell (PSC): a type of stem cell with the capacity to differentiate into almost any cell or to generate any of the three primary germ layers (ectoderm, mesoderm, and endoderm).

Synthetic biology: an interdisciplinary field that enables the artificial engineering of genetic circuits to selectively control cellular processes or responses by combining the parts of different organisms into new biological systems.

Tissue engineering (TE): a multidisciplinary field that combines principles from engineering, cell biology, and materials science to develop biological substitutes that can restore, maintain, or improve the function of damaged or diseased tissues or organs.

Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM): an autoimmune disease characterized by the loss of insulin-producing β cells leading to sustained hyperglycemia. It accounts for ~5% of cases of diabetes mellitus. The main aim of T1DM treatment is to recover the insulin-producing function by either administering exogenous insulin or replacing the β cell mass.

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM): the most common type of diabetes mellitus, marked by elevated circulating glucose

reproducible bioprinting of highly functional pancreatic constructs to be used in islet replacement therapy for T1DM, resulting in a prevascularized and ready-to-function engineered endocrine pancreas, which could circumvent major hurdles of islet transplantation, such as poor engraftment and islet loss due to inflammatory insults and immune system reactions. Cell encapsulation strategies primarily aim to protect endocrine cells from immune rejection by avoiding or reducing immunosuppressant drug administration. By contrast, bioprinting offers a more comprehensive solution by incorporating endocrine and structural vascular components and 3D architectural features to improve cell survival, integration, and long-term functionality [8–10].

Bioprinting approaches for engineering an endocrine pancreas

Recent years have seen increasing interest in 3D bioprinting, since controlling the geometry of engineered tissues and the 3D positioning of different cell types directly influences diffusion distances, nutrient exchange rate, distribution of mechanical forces, cell–cell communication, and cell behavior [11,12].

Although bioprinting has been extensively leveraged historically for producing hard, connective tissues, namely bone and cartilage, recently it has shown potential to engineer soft tissues, including the pancreas [13,14]. Several approaches can be used to achieve this, including extrusion-based, inkjet-based, and laser-assisted bioprinting [13,15,16]. Extrusion-based bioprinting is the technique most reported for biofabrication, with notable examples of pancreas TE, since this technique allows the seamless deposition of a range of materials and cell types [17,18].

However, two aspects require careful consideration in extrusion bioprinting, especially when dealing with sensitive biological materials and cellular aggregates, such as islets, namely the bioprinting speed and exposure to shear stress [19] (Figure 1). Similar to most biofabrication techniques, extrusion-based bioprinting builds 3D structures in a layer-by-layer fashion, which affects the biofabrication speed [20]. This is especially relevant for larger constructs, because longer bioprinting times increase cell or organoid exposure to the bioprinter cartridge and mechanical stress [19,21]. Although versatile, extrusion bioprinting limits the geometrical complexity of structures that can be achieved. Digital light processing (DLP) bioprinting was recently leveraged to encapsulate **induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)**-derived islets in gelatin methacrylate (GelMA)-based constructs. However, the printing speed remains a limiting factor because this is a layer-based technique, and light shadowing of the islets could affect the printability of complex structures [22].

More recently, methods have been developed to create large, clinically relevant biofabricated grafts quickly and efficiently while overcoming the aforementioned limitations. **Volumetric bioprinting (VBP)** (Box 2), a light-based bioprinting technology, has been developed as a solution to enhance the speed of printing and bypass the geometric limitations of traditional layer-by-layer methods [23]. Given that VBP operates in a contactless, mechanical stress-free manner, fragile cells and organoids have been already printed with superior viability to outcomes with extrusion-based techniques (Figure 1) [24]. Consequently, this technique could be extensively leveraged to generate pancreatic models and directly print islets from different sources. Alternatively, other light-based volumetric fabrication techniques, including dual-color light-sheet printing, which can print products within minutes, could be of interest [25].

A crucial aspect that needs careful consideration when generating an accurate bioprinted construct is that, once the appropriate spatial placement of cells and materials is achieved, the biological constructs are required to undergo maturation and morphogenesis. Therefore, the presence of a supporting stromal network, involving vasculature and innervation, is vital for the

levels due to insufficient insulin production resulting from increased peripheral insulin resistance or β cell dysfunction, metabolic stress, and inflammation. It accounts for ~90–95% of cases of diabetes mellitus. Exogenous insulin is also used as treatment for T2DM but, given the disease complexity, other drugs, such as insulin sensitizers and insulin release stimulators, can be required [100]. Currently available drugs cause several side effects that negatively impact patients' quality of life. Moreover, these drugs are designed only to manage symptoms rather than address the root causes of the disease. Therefore, there is a critical need for robust T2DM disease models that can accurately replicate the complex pathophysiology of T2DM.

Volumetric bioprinting (VBP): a bioprinting technique that enables the 3D printing of structures within a bioink using light-patterning techniques. Unlike traditional layer-by-layer bioprinting methods, VBP allows for a layer-less and ultrafast fabrication of complex 3D structures within a bulk volume.

Trends In Biotechnology

Figure 1. Toolkit for endocrine pancreas bioprinting. The generation of human pancreatic islets from pluripotent stem cells (PSCs) involves a seven-stage differentiation protocol: definitive endoderm stage (DE); posterior gut tube stage (PGT); two pancreatic progenitor stage (PP1 and PP2); endocrine progenitor stage (EP); and differentiated islet stage, which are further matured in the seventh stage. Support cells, such as vascular, neural, and stromal cells, are needed to generate a more accurate functional model. Different bioprinting approaches, including digital light processing (DLP), extrusion bioprinting, volumetric bioprinting (VBP), and the combination thereof, termed Embedded-extrusion Volumetric Printing (EmVP), can be leveraged to obtain clinically relevant-sized endocrine pancreatic models. Bioprinting the endocrine pancreas is a multifaceted and complex process that requires careful consideration of the printing technique, and choice of bioinks, and cell sources. Research should focus on combining biomaterial and bioprinting technologies with highly advanced human biological models, such as induced (i)PSC-derived β cells, to improve the success of their application as *in vitro* models and their translation to the clinic. Synergy between bioprinting and other domains of tissue engineering, including stem cell and molecular biology, can also open additional possibilities for more advanced models with enhanced functionality and efficacy.

long-term maintenance, viability, and steering of the behavior of large-scale tissues. 3D bioprinting can be leveraged to incorporate such surrounding stromal compartments into an engineered construct. This is especially appealing for the endocrine pancreas, which has an intricate system of islets with neural and vascular networks that impact islet maturation, characterized by an insulin secretion capacity and functionality [26–28].

The presence of a functional vascular network not only sustains endocrine cell viability, but also enhances glucose sensitivity and improves the potency and efficiency of insulin secretion [29]. Moreover, autonomic innervation, including parasympathetic and sympathetic inputs, modulates insulin secretion by fine tuning β cell responsiveness to glucose fluctuations and regulating intra-islet blood flow [30]. In addition, both the stiffness and composition of the 3D structures can be adjusted to support and promote the maturation of immature insulin-secreting cells, which can

Box 2. Volumetric bioprinting, a light-based bioprinting technology

Volumetric bioprinting (VPB) is a cutting-edge technology that has the potential to revolutionize the field of tissue engineering and regenerative medicine. Inspired by optical tomography, this approach differs from traditional 3D bioprinting methods because it does not rely on layer-by-layer deposition, but instead leverages a series of 2D light projections. These light patterns are delivered from various angles into a vial containing a bioresin, typically a cell-laden light-responsive hydrogel. Accumulation of these light patterns results in an anisotropic 3D dose distribution, which initiates polymerization of the bioresin only in areas that match the predesigned object. A significant advantage of VBP is the mechanical stress-free impact on the cells, ensuring their viability and functionality after printing. Furthermore, it can fabricate tissues at an impressive speed regardless of the model dimension, making it a promising tool for creating large-scale functional organs.

VBP has been successfully used in several applications, such as to fabricate living constructs laden with either single cells or organoids. By chemically matching the refractive indexes of the biomaterial to the embedded cells or by leveraging a scattering correction algorithm before computing the 2D projections, it is possible to obtain functional constructs with high resolution even in presence of high cell density and high-scattering formulations. An interesting application involved the printing in <20 s of functional liver units capable of performing key toxin elimination processes similar to those performed *in vivo*. In addition to liver tissues, VBP has also been used for the fabrication of several types of tissue, including pancreas, bone, cartilage, vascular grafts, and neural tissue. Despite these promising advancements, further research is needed to overcome limitations, including the loss of non-crosslinked biomaterial, eventually loaded with cells.

Thus, VBP is a promising technology with significant potential. The ability to quickly and efficiently create complex and functional tissues renders it a valuable tool in the quest to address the organ donor shortage and improve *in vitro* models. As research continues, we can expect even more exciting developments, bringing us closer to the being able to create large-scale and clinically relevant biofabricated constructs.

then be integrated into the bioengineered platform [31–33]. Therefore, multi-material and multi-cellular bioprinting ability is a crucial consideration when selecting the printing process for endocrine pancreas constructs. For instance, by using sacrificial **bioinks** or multicellular bioprinting approaches, researchers created complex tubular networks within bioprinted tissues [34–36], including the pancreas [13]. By leveraging these techniques and patterning the spatial architecture, it is possible to provide the necessary signaling cues to the bioprinted cells, enhancing their survival and function over time. For instance, these tubular structures can be colonized by pro-angiogenic cells, establishing a vascularized structure [37]. Moreover, bioprinting of tissues embedded with neural networks has also been reported [38], with innervated muscle tissues generated by using a co-axial nozzle to bioprint aligned muscle fibers and neural cells. This technology could be adapted for the bioengineering of an endocrine pancreas, allowing for the creation of vascularized or innervated islets. More specifically, multimaterial VBP can be achieved either via a sequential approach, leveraging multiple bioresins containing different cell types, or by combining VBP with extrusion bioprinting, using the support bath as a bioresin to be subsequently sculpted by light [16,39].

Notably, with the emergence of novel bioprinting techniques, a key research focus is integrating multiple methods in a multi-modal process to leverage their complementary strengths. For example, VBP and embedded-extrusion bioprinting were recently combined to leverage the ability of VBP to shape hydrogels into complex geometries with the ability of extrusion printing to obtain multicellular/multi-material prints. To prove this concept, a pancreatic model was produced with controlled spatial arrangement of engineered β cells in a human mesenchymal stem cell (MSC)-laden environment [10]. This showed how complex cm^3 -scale pancreatic models could be generated in <30 s by combining insulin-releasing units with different stromal populations via a multi-material approach.

Cell-based building blocks for pancreas bioprinting and bioengineering

Pancreatic islet cells

A pivotal aspect for bioprinting the endocrine pancreas is to develop a stable source of islets. While the isolation of primary human islets appears to be an intuitive way of obtaining a cell source

for bioprinting, there are several issues to overcome. First, only a limited amount of islets can be isolated from a single donor and, due to the intrinsic nature of tissue disaggregation and separation from the exocrine cells, the recovery rate ranges from 48% to 72%, depending on factors such as donor age or body mass index [40,41]. Second, isolated islets present varying degrees of purity based on the isolation process. They lack the ability to proliferate *in vitro* while maintaining their glucose responsiveness and maturity, and show a loss in terms of islet count and functionality when cultured for longer than 6–8 days [42,43]. Thus, to obtain sufficient cells for high-throughput production of *in vitro* models or, more ambitiously, for therapeutic transplantation, pooling cells from multiple HLA-matched donors would be necessary. However, this option is limited by the current donor organ shortage and by challenges posed by highly heterogeneous genetic donor backgrounds, leading to the need for strict immunosuppression regimens and a persistent risk of transplant rejection, which might affect both research and clinical outcomes [5,44]. There have been attempts to generate immortalized human β cell lines from insulinomas, namely EndoC- β H1-3, which can be massively expanded [45]. Nevertheless, these platforms present several downsides limiting their applications, including the risk that immortalization genes remain active after the expansion procedure, or that these spheroids only contain β -like cells and lack other islet cell types, limiting their application to disease modeling. Porcine islets are a readily available source of islets for modeling platform for drug screening, although the inter-species differences could affect their modeling potential.

Generating islets from **pluripotent stem cells (PSCs)** can circumvent the abovementioned problems, offering an unlimited supply of islets for bioprinting. The first PSC differentiation protocols were developed during the early 2000s [46–48], inspired by pancreatic developmental biology (Box 1), where PSCs are primed towards the definitive endoderm to further differentiate into pancreatic progenitor cells and finally into islets. Nevertheless, these first differentiation protocols yielded immature endocrine cells that showed a poor glucose-responsive profile. Recent advances in stem cell differentiation technologies resulted in finely tuned differentiation protocols to generate more mature β cells with increased insulin secretion capacity [49–52]. Nevertheless, challenges remain (Figure 2), such as the presence of multihormonal cells and a glucose

Figure 2. Main challenges to developing a functional pancreatic endocrine models based on pluripotent stem cells (PSCs). Different aspects need to be addressed when leveraging PSCs as biological building blocks for tissue engineering. Matching the endocrine population heterogeneity and functionality of native islets, growing a vasculature network for a better integration and survival of the islets and avoiding islet mis-segregation and rejection are among the main hurdles.

sensitivity and subsequent hormonal response that does not match that of healthy human native islets. Lower functionality results partly from the fact that differentiation protocols yield poorly understood side populations, such as enterochromaffin-like cells, although whether they represent a transient or immature cell type [53], or an undesired side-population [49,54] remains unclear. Current research is focusing on further understanding the multiple populations arising from differentiated cells using single-omics and lineage-tracing platforms [53–55].

To obtain enough islets for bioprinting, high-throughput modeling, or clinical use, more efficient and mass-scalable manufacturing and differentiation of PSCs are vital. Currently, PSC differentiation protocols are typically performed manually in static adherent cultures that are difficult to scale-up, and are highly operator dependent. However, human (h)PSCs as cellular aggregates can be cultured and differentiated in suspension bioreactors amenable to scaling-up, and compatible with automated monitoring/control of the culture environment [48,56,57]. Nevertheless, PSC aggregates can differentiate via nonselective and poorly understood mechanisms, and not all cells within the aggregate have equal access to the soluble factors needed during differentiation. This is especially relevant in the context of pancreatic tissue bioprinting, since the differentiation of PSCs to early-stage pancreatic endocrine cells is more efficient in monolayers compared with suspension cultures [58,59].

A further advantage of using PSCs, specifically **induced (i)PSCs**, is the potential for personalized modeling and medicine. Autologous or allogeneic iPSCs allow the production of pancreatic β cells matching the genetic background of the recipient, increasing the translatability of a cellular model or dramatically reducing rejection risks in the clinic [60]. Moreover, recent studies have shown that iPSCs can be genetically engineered to have an hypimmune profile via HLA ablation [61]. Generating islets from hypimmune iPSCs was recently reported and initial animal experiments showed immune evasion and tuned glucose control in murine and nonhuman primate models [62–64]. Nevertheless, there are risks that need to be weighed against the advantage of using this approach. While immune evasion is pivotal to ensure islet survival in patients with T1DM, it could render the cells reservoirs for (viral) infections, or could cause uncontrolled growth of proliferative cells, which, in the case of undifferentiated pluripotent cells, could lead to teratoma formation or malignancy.

Finally, an additional approach for the generation of pancreatic islets is the *trans*-differentiation of proliferative cells derived from other tissues. This has been proven successful when *trans*-differentiating hepatocytes [65] and gastric stem cells [66]. While these sources of cells present similar advantages to PSCs in terms of expansion capacity and the high-throughput generation of endocrine cells, their *trans*-differentiation remains limited to the use of gene transfer vectors to steer their transcriptomic profile. While these approaches could allow the production of (patient-specific) cells for disease modeling and drug testing, the use of gene-edited cells for clinical application requires stringent safety and regulatory assessments.

The peri-islet cellular niche

Signals, such as morphogens and regulatory cytokines, from pancreatic endocrine niche cells, including pericytes, endothelial cells, or peripheral nervous system cells, namely Schwann cells, are vital for steering islet maturation and functionality. Stimuli and signals derived from the cellular microenvironment, promote the acquisition of function during the neonatal stage [4,53]. Indeed, bio-engineering platforms designed to have other types of cell alongside endocrine components presenting an immature phenotype, such as neonatal porcine islets or PSC-derived β -cells, can support islet maturation and function [33,67,68]. Thus, bioprinting strategies that enable spatial patterning of multiple cell types are vital for recreating a functional endocrine pancreas

resembling the *in vivo* situation. For instance, bioprinting techniques have been extensively explored to provide vessel-like, endothelialized structures [69], which would be a step closer to fully prevascularized endocrine constructs, helping to improve vascular engrafting and limit hypoxic stress upon transplantation. Moreover, in *in vitro* disease modeling, vascularization can allow the study of behaviors such as perfusion of drugs and biodistribution within islet-rich constructs, which are difficult to investigate in current models. Model tissues are typically made with primary vascular cells, such as human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) or cord blood-derived endothelial colony-forming cells (ECFCs). These are valuable for *in vitro* studies but are usually allogeneic, creating logistical and immunocompatibility challenges for prevascularized transplants, often requiring strong immunosuppression. Thus, patient-specific support cells derived from iPSCs or HLA-depleted PSCs could be used to generate a fully prevascularized and ready-to-function pancreatic endocrine graft while displaying reduced rejection risks in clinical settings. There are similar considerations for bioprinting endocrine pancreas, including mesenchymal cells and Schwann cells, which, although understudied, could steer the insulin release capacity and maturation of pancreatic islets [53,70] and, thus, will likely be a focus of research for future biofabrication efforts.

Selection of bioinks/bioresins for islet culture

Selecting a biomaterial that mimics the mechanical and physicochemical characteristics of the target tissue and supports cell embedding is crucial for bioprinting a functional endocrine pancreas. Such biomaterials, also referred to as bioinks or bioresins in the context of extrusion- and light-based printing, respectively, must provide a favorable environment for the cells during and after bioprinting. Ideally, islet encapsulation should be devoid of harmful mechanical or chemical stress [71,72], and the selected biomaterials should maintain an optimal porosity and mass exchange profile to ensure diffusion of oxygen, nutrients, small molecules, and growth factors [16] required for cell survival and differentiation [72].

Furthermore, the biomaterial itself must provide a suitable environment to support the cells but still remain bioprintable, a requirement closely tied to the selected bioprinting method. Although soft matrices, such as Matrigel, provide a favorable environment for cell culture, they are unsuitable for extrusion-based bioprinting because they cannot be sculpted and tend to deform immediately after deposition. By contrast, light-based bioprinting requires a bioink with a specific photopolymerization threshold and a nontoxic photoinitiator, enabling its spatially selective light crosslinking.

Hydrogel-based bioinks, often derived from natural materials, namely alginate, gelatin, or hyaluronic acid, have shown promising results because of their biocompatibility, printability, and tunable mechanical properties [28,73]. However, alginate encapsulation can lead to pericapsular fibrosis overgrowth, causing the islets to become ischemic or unresponsive to glucose spikes. This could be avoided by the addition of small molecules or by tuning the polymer composition (e.g., guluronate content) [74]. By contrast, GelMa-based bioinks [75] have been successfully studied to encapsulate PSC-derived β cells. This study showed that 405 nm photocrosslinking with lithium phenyl-2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl-phosphinate (LAP) safely stabilized encapsulated islets, which remained viable for 7 days, supporting polymer hydrogels as a suitable strategy for bioprinting pancreatic endocrine constructs.

A functional bioprinted pancreas requires not only long-term viability and functionality of bioprinted islets, but also active interactions between pancreatic cells and the bioink. In addition, the model should allow the integration of other cell types to create a multicellular system [71,76,77]. The current challenge in the field is selecting biomaterials that support the survival and function of islet and vascular cells for bioprinting an endocrine pancreas. Different cell types require specific biomaterials with

tailored properties, such as stiffness, porosity, or viscoelasticity. While vascular cells require highly porous and permissive materials with attachment motives to better stretch and form connections, pancreatic islets require a matrix that prevent sprouting and disaggregation [10,26].

Decellularized extracellular matrix (dECM)-based materials, derived from specific tissues, could be an alternative bioink, offering a native-like microenvironment in which key factors to support islets, vascular, and stromal cells are partly retained [78]. In the native pancreas, ECM is involved in regulating cellular processes, such as endocrine secretion, proliferation or apoptosis inhibition [79,80]. The most abundant ECM components are laminins, type IV collagen, and hyaluronic acid, which acts as a stabilizing component and has been shown to protect β cells from oxidative stress [26,81]. For instance, endocrine cells embedded in decellularized lung dECM-based scaffolds [82,83] were reported to be efficient at reverting diabetes in a murine model. This biomaterial was used to promote the endocrine-secreting function of immature endocrine cells and vascularization in an *in vitro* setting [33]. Over a week-long culture period, the bioengineered vasculature surrounded the dECM-encapsulated (functional) islets, leading to the creation of a ready-to-transplant, vascularized endocrine organ. Moreover, dECM can be processed to obtain tissue-specific bioinks, making it possible to take advantage of organ-target dECM cues coupled with the 3D-bioprinting option to reshape organ architecture. Pancreatic dECM hydrogels have been used to improve the function of vascularized islet constructs [84]. Here, as a result of human pancreatic dECM, human islets show increased glucose- and KCl-stimulated insulin secretion and improved mitochondrial function compared with islets cultured without dECM. In addition, RNA sequencing of human islets cultured in dECM confirmed an improved gene ontology signature of terms related to extracellular signaling and adhesion. Recent work also demonstrated that pancreatic dECM bioinks can be used in extrusion bioprinting techniques to sustain the bioactivity of PSC-derived islets [78], introducing the capacity to produce porous architectures beneficial for insulin diffusion. Moreover, because bioresins made entirely from dECM from multiple tissues are also suitable and printable via VBP [85], future advances are expected to also leverage light-based bioprinting techniques to produce islet-laden structures at higher resolution. To achieve dECM photopolymerization, tyrosine residue-carrying proteins are leveraged to form di-tyrosine crosslinks [86,87] after photoactivation in the presence of tris(2,2-bipyridyl) dichlororuthenium(II) hexahydrate and sodium persulfate (Ru/SPS) as photoinitiator system. Alternatively, dECM inks have also been modified with photo-reactive chemical groups (i.e., acryloyl) [85].

Despite promising advances, considerable challenges remain for *in vivo* translation and clinical applications. Most notably, islet transplantation often requires immunosuppression to counter allogeneic rejection and autoimmune reactions typical of T1DM. Maintaining islet function while the graft can evade the host immune system is crucial for future bioprinted construct-based therapies. Biomaterials are a first line of defense against immune rejection for embedded islets, but islet function is strictly dependent on their access to vasculature to sense glucose levels. Encapsulation in bioinert biomaterials, such as alginate hydrogels, can provide islets with an appropriate microenvironment [88], allowing nutrient and insulin diffusion but preventing the immune cells from entering the matrix [89]. A recent strategy was developed by co-delivering allogeneic islets with streptavidin (SA)–FasL–presenting microgels [90], which resulted in sustained glycemic control, and graft survival in diabetic nonhuman primates for more than 6 months. This material-based immunomodulatory approach proved translational potential in β cell replacement without the need for long-term immunosuppression.

Overall, the selection of bioinks (Table 1) for the bioprinting of pancreatic endocrine tissues is a multifaceted requirement that needs careful consideration of the interplay between the desired physical properties, biological functions, and immunoprotection. Thus, it is crucial to make this

Table 1. Suitable bioinks/bioresins for bioprinting an endocrine pancreas

Bioink	Printing method	Resolution	Pancreatic cell source	Strengths	Limitations	Refs		
Alginate	Extrusion bioprinting	400–600 μm	Porcine primary islets	Cell-friendly physical crosslinking Immunoprotective due to its inert properties	Possible quick degradation Inert material, lacking motifs for cell adhesion	[28]		
		400 μm	MIN-6 β -cell line			[113]		
Alginate/methylcellulose	Extrusion bioprinting	610–840 μm	Rat primary islets			Human primary islets and human PSC-derived islets	[114]	
		410 μm					[115]	
dECM	Embedded-extrusion bioprinting	250–350 μm	Human PSC-derived islets	Maintains physiological microenvironments components of source tissue (e.g., growth factors, structural proteins) Facilitated co-culture of different cell types because of physiological-like properties Presence of attachment motifs able to promote cell self-organization	Decellularization protocols might cause collagen denaturation Combination with other support polymers often required to enhance stability Not immunoprotective	[116]		
		200 μm	Human PSC-derived islets			[78]		
dECM/HAMA	DLP	200 μm	Rat primary islets			Presence of attachment motifs able to promote cell self-organization Bioactive material able to promote ECM production from encapsulated cells Thermoresponsive properties to improve printability	Not immunoprotective Batch-to-batch variation in characteristics of starting polymer	[22]
GelMA/alginate	Extrusion bioprinting	400 μm	Murine primary islets			[117]		
Defined protein blend (fibrinogen, gelatin, hyaluronic acid)	Extrusion bioprinting	300 μm	Murine PSC-derived islets	Defined blend of proteins Presence of attachment motifs able to promote cell self-organization Enables tuning of material blend to fit co-culture needs	Not immunoprotective Possible quick degradation	[13]		
Collagen type 1	Embedded-extrusion bioprinting	32–60 μm	MIN-6 β -cell line	Defined matrix Presence of attachment motifs able to promote cell self-organization Bioactive material able to promote ECM production from encapsulated cells	Not immunoprotective	[118]		

selection based on the primary goal of the bioprinted constructs, whether it is for tissue modeling, where bioactive materials are crucial to ensure the generation of multicellular structures, or for translation, where the immunoprotective characteristics of the biomaterial present advantages. Future research should focus on developing bioinks that can meet all these requirements, paving the way for successful endocrine pancreas biofabrication.

Bioprinting the endocrine pancreas and synthetic biology: toward converging fields

The field of TE and, by extension, bioprinting has primarily focused on advancing novel biofabrication tools and biomaterials to tune organoid and cell behavior with the surrounding 3D microenvironment and microarchitecture [11,12,91]. Nevertheless, engineered and bioprinted tissues still lack the complexity of their *in vivo* counterparts. There is an urgent need to develop and implement novel strategies that replicate cellular environments and developmental conditions. These advances should aim to not only enhance current therapeutic approaches, but

also address critical knowledge gaps in the field, such as improving islet development, understanding the factors influencing islet differentiation and organization, determining the role of different proportions of endocrine cells, and elucidating their interactions with the ECM, its composition, and surrounding cells. The possibility of triggering biological processes or patterning cellular behaviors and functions within a bioprinter, for instance to trigger morphogen or transcription factor signals in an asymmetrical spatial way, could revolutionize the field of TE and bioprinting by shifting the current paradigm of simply sculpting cells into a desired architecture, paving the way to accurately recapitulate the situation *in vivo*. Synthetic biology uses newly genetically engineered modules to craft and control cellular behaviors or interactions (Box 3) enabling fine regulation of specific biological processes on demand [92]. Converging bioprinting with synthetic cell engineering can harness the synergistic strengths of both technologies to control the architecture and physical cues experienced by cells and organoids, and introduce programmable cellular behaviors and functions through targeted gene editing or the incorporation of synthetic genetic responsive circuits.

Recent research has showcased the potential of these converging technologies to pattern cells in a 3D setting while orthogonally programming gene expression via genetically engineered circuits controlled by small molecules [93] or temperature [94], resulting in asymmetrical control of cell types and their behavior. In addition, synthetic biology systems have also been used to mimic disease development. For example, TE and optogenetics have been used to selectively induce

Box 3. Synthetic biology approaches for tissue engineering and bioprinting

Synthetic biology aims to engineer genetic circuits to selectively control cellular responses by combining parts of different organisms into new biological systems. It has been used to develop novel solutions for various applications, from healthcare to agriculture and environmental sustainability, and is receiving increased attention in eukaryotic cell and organoid biology research. Significant recent advances in synthetic biology tools allow researchers to modulate several aspects of cellular behavior, including cellular juxtacrine and paracrine signaling, cell adhesion, and controlling cell fate by harnessing different stimuli. For example, optogenetic systems have been developed that couple bacterial or fungi phytochromes with eukaryotic proteins, such as gene activators or location peptides, to trigger downstream gene expression (TtCBD [99] or BphP1 [107,108] optogenetic switches) or protein relocation (LEXY inducible nuclear export [109]) upon light illumination. Other examples include engineered juxtacrine signaling, which couples a cellular receptor with a transcription factor or gene activator to trigger downstream gene expression once bound to the receptor target (SynNotch [110] or OCAR systems [111]), and artificial circuits, which have been implemented in the pancreatic field to drive pancreatic progenitor differentiation [96] or trigger gastric stem cell *trans*-differentiation into functional pancreatic β cells [66].

Such platforms could be used to overcome major hurdles in bioprinting and tissue engineering. Traditional methods for generating organoids and cell-laden bioprinted constructs are based on the delivery of small molecules or protein and have recently evolved toward the engineering of novel materials and matrices to enable cells to thrive. Nevertheless, these simplistic methods fail to replicate the intricate spatial arrangement and signals found during organ development, resulting in oversimplistic organoids and bioprinted constructs. Combining bioprinting with novel genetic engineering through synthetic biology could improve not only the functionality of engineered constructs, but also spatial asymmetric and dynamic control for recapitulating and rewiring developmental processes, paving the way for more advanced and reliable bioprinted constructs.

Successful implementation of engineered genetic circuits in applied settings requires careful consideration of several key factors. First, the design of synthetic circuits must account for both the efficiency of gene transfer and the required duration of gene expression. Viral vectors, such as lentiviruses and adeno-associated viruses (AAVs), enable highly efficient gene transfer; however, their therapeutic application can be limited due to potential immune responses [112], in contrast to plasmid-based systems. In addition, while non-integrative vectors (e.g., plasmids, mRNA, or AAVs) enable transient gene expression, integrative platforms, such as lentiviral vectors, transposase-based systems (i.e., Sleeping Beauty), or CRISPR/Cas9-mediated integration, offer prolonged and stable expression of the engineered construct. Nonetheless, these integrative approaches present challenges, including random genomic insertion and the potential for prolonged expression of genes that may only be required transiently. Another critical consideration is the potential for unintended basal expression, or leakiness, which does not enable binary (On/Off) gene expression and is observed in widely used systems, including the TET-ON system or optogenetic circuits, which can result in gene expression even in the absence of the intended activator. Therefore, optimizing synthetic circuits requires balancing the advantages and limitations of these platforms to achieve the desired efficacy, robustness, and safety.

tumor growth in an (intestinal) organ-on-a-chip platform by using light in a spatially controlled manner [95].

The field of pancreatic TE could benefit significantly from these technologies. First, access to highly functional β cells is restricted, either because of donor shortage or the inherent limitations of PSC differentiation. To overcome this, synthetic biology has been used to develop genetic circuits to efficiently control cellular fate in PSCs toward insulin-secreting β cells via vanillic acid-induced expression of *PDX1*, *NGN3*, and *MAFA* [96] to swiftly and reproducibly generate functional β cells. Although providing full control over cell differentiation is appealing, synthetic biology has also been used to strip to the minimum the key functionality of β cells, their insulin secretion capacity, in a controlled and timely fashion in response to varying glucose concentrations. Leveraging synthetic biology, this function can be applied to almost any cell type, in a controllable, and minimally invasive fashion with remote physical fields by using optogenetic and sonogenetic approaches. Researchers have engineered cells to successfully control insulin release in response to light [97] or vibrations [98], resulting in on-demand secretion and diabetes control in murine models. Synthetic biology has also been harnessed to promote endogenous insulin secretion in a mouse model by engineering cells with a light-operated GLP1 expression mechanism [99] activated with green light, leading to the efficient control of circulating glucose levels in mice.

Despite the potential of synthetic biology, there have been few attempts to merge this field with TE and bioprinting, tools that would be especially relevant for not only pancreatic TE, but the field as a whole. Recently, bioprinted pancreatic constructs with engineered β cells were demonstrated that contained a synthetic construct comprising melanopsin as stimuli receptor, and membrane depolarization-induced release of intracellular vesicles as actuating mechanism, thus allowing rapid, on-demand insulin release upon illumination with blue light [16]. Bioprinting was needed to build structures laden with high densities of the engineered β cells, which remained highly functional only when cell–cell contact are facilitated. Although preliminary, this approach indicates how synthetic biology could significantly transform pancreas bioprinting and TE. Such transformation is expected to culminate in the development of the next generation of *in vitro* models and engineered constructs, which will more accurately emulate the intricate functionalities of native organs or provide increased functionality of the developed constructs.

Concluding remarks and future perspectives

Diabetes treatment remains challenging despite advances in treatment options and disease management. The complexity of replicating the innate functionality of pancreatic islets underscores the difficulty in developing effective long-term treatments. The current mainstay treatment, exogenous insulin administration, fails to replicate physiological glucose homeostasis, and the only curative treatment, islet transplantation, is hampered by the availability of donor tissue and need for immunosuppression. These limitations highlight the pressing need for novel therapeutic approaches.

Bioprinting and TE present promising avenues for addressing these challenges (Figure 2). The integration of bioprinting with stem cell technology could circumvent the current donor shortage and lead to the generation of patient-specific islets and prevascularized pancreatic constructs, enhancing the potential for personalized disease modeling and, ultimately, personalized medicine (Figure 3). However, significant challenges remain and future research should not only focus on improving differentiation protocols for PSCs to produce more mature and functional islets, but also further explore how shape (i.e. islet size, geometry, and surrounding micro and macro structures) and surrounding cells affect islet maturation. In addition, efforts to engineer and bioprint a vascularized and innervated pancreatic microenvironment could significantly improve the functionality and longevity of implanted constructs [22,28,33,82] (see Outstanding questions).

Outstanding questions

How can differentiation protocols be used to increase the purity, maturation, and functionality of PSC-derived islets?

How does the architecture engineered via TE and bioprinting impact functionality or differentiation by tuning islet confinement and matrix interaction?

What is the future of PSC-derived islet treatments, and should we prioritize using general allogeneic embryonic stem cells within an immune evasive matrix/device or focus on personalized iPSC treatments, including immunoevasive cells?

How can vascularization and an immunoprotective capacity be merged within a bioprinted construct? Can inert biomaterials providing immunoenhancing vascularization be combined with the presence of small molecules to modulate the immune system?

Can bioprinted pancreatic constructs solve the current problems associated with islet transplantation, namely low grafting rate and low islet survival, by generating a ready-to-function, immunoprivileged, and vascularized pancreatic tissue?

How will the synergy between bioprinting and synthetic biology better recapitulate the *in vivo* situation in *in vitro* systems?

What synthetic biology tools are required to enable precise shaping of tissue structure and function within bioprinting?

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Figure 3. Synergizing synthetic biology with bioprinting strategies and its building blocks to fabricate more complex models. Advances in bioprinting technologies, biomaterial development, synthetic biology, and stem cell engineering have paved the way for the creation of bioinspired systems that more closely replicate the composition and function of the endocrine pancreas. These technologies offer the potential to develop advanced *in vitro* models for drug testing, finely tuning the interaction of pancreatic endocrine cells with the surrounding extracellular matrix (ECM) or stromal cellular component, and fully functional pancreatic constructs for therapeutic applications.

Converging bioprinting and synthetic biology can offer significant advances in TE to replicate the *in vivo* complexity, opening new horizons for enhanced control over cellular behaviors in a spatio-temporal-dependent manner (Figure 3). Advanced bioprinting techniques need to be developed that can be merged with synthetic genetic circuits when possible, refining the precision of bioprinting and integrating programmable cellular modules to fulfill the ultimate goal of developing bioprinted tissues for regenerative medicine, and disease modeling (see Outstanding questions).

Although diabetes remains an incurable disease, rapid advances in bioprinting and synthetic biology hold promise for developing more effective treatments. By refining these technologies and addressing existing challenges (Box 4), TE pancreatic constructs are revolutionizing therapeutic screening and it is conceivable that bioprinted pancreatic implants could one day provide a viable solution to the organ shortage crisis and revolutionize the management of diabetes.

Box 4. Overcoming challenges and limitations of bioprinted endocrine pancreatic constructs

While bioprinting strategies combined with stem cell biology and synthetic biology offer a promising avenue for developing advanced models and therapies for diabetes, several significant challenges and limitations remain, in addition to the lengthy regulatory pathway toward the approval of (engineered) cell-based therapeutics. Addressing these obstacles is critical to translating these approaches into clinically viable solutions.

One primary concern is ensuring the functional viability of stem cell-derived pancreatic islets and other cell types following bioprinting, with a particular focus on selecting biomaterials and media compositions that will enable the maintenance and function of the multicellular structure. The co-culture of islets with other supportive cell types, such as vascular cells, Schwann cells and mesenchymal stromal cells, presents a technical challenge. These supporting cells have critical roles in islet function and survival, yet achieving an optimal balance within bioprinted constructs remains difficult. Spatial organization and controlled cell–cell interactions need to be fine-tuned to replicate the native pancreatic microenvironment effectively. Similarly, successful engraftment and long-term function of bioprinted pancreatic constructs rely on establishment of a robust vascular network to provide an adequate oxygen and nutrient supply. Current approaches struggle to efficiently mimic native vascularization, leading to necrosis and functional decline over time. Although the integration of endothelial cells and pro-angiogenic factors into bioprinted constructs has shown promise, further refinement is necessary to enhance perfusion and sustain long-term viability.

Another aspect requiring attention is that, while light-based bioprinting technologies present several advantages compared with conventional extrusion printing, such as avoiding shear stress, they still encounter additional challenges related to print resolution and accuracy because of scattering and shadowing effects derived from the organoids and cells. These can impair the precision of printed constructs, affecting cell placement and tissue architecture. In turn, this could prevent the bioprinted structure from easily reaching the therapeutic concentration of organoids required for circulating glucose homeostasis. Advanced computational modeling to edit the wavefront of the projected light and adaptive optics are potential approaches to overcome these constraints. Moreover, the development of novel crosslinkers that could enable the use of near infrared light to crosslink materials could overcome these limitations, owing to their superior penetration depth within scattering biological media.

Furthermore, implantation of bioprinted pancreatic constructs also poses hurdles, particularly in ensuring rapid engraftment and preventing fibrosis. The host immune response can lead to fibrotic encapsulation of the construct, impairing its function and reducing its therapeutic efficacy. Immunomodulatory strategies, biomaterial optimization, and synthetic biology interventions are being explored to mitigate these issues.

Finally, synthetic biology tools face hurdles to achieving efficient delivery, stable expression, and controlled regulation. Leakage of gene expression and variability in synthetic circuits can lead to unintended effects, necessitating precise control mechanisms. Strategies such as further optimization of inducible gene expression systems [108], optimized viral and non-viral delivery systems, and genetic circuits with different levels of control [92] (i.e., combination of optogenetics with small molecule-triggered gene induction) are being developed to address these concerns.

Overcoming these limitations will require interdisciplinary efforts integrating bioengineering, materials science, cell biology, and computational modeling. Advances in vascularization strategies, biomaterial design, synthetic circuit precision, and immunomodulatory approaches will be essential for the successful modeling and clinical translation of bioprinted pancreatic constructs for diabetes therapy.

Author contributions

D.R. and P.C. contributed equally to this work. Conceptualization: D.R., P.C., R.L.; investigation: D.R., P.C.; resources: D.R., P.C., R.L.; writing—original draft: D.R., P.C.; writing—review & editing: C.P., A.C., R.L.; supervision: R.L.; funding acquisition: R.L. All authors ensured that questions on the accuracy or integrity of all parts of the manuscript were appropriately researched and resolved.

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Declaration of interests

R.L. is scientific advisor for Readily3D, which was not involved in this study. The other authors declare no competing interests.

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